

Characters and BPH resistance score for varieties^a bred at ARS, Maruteru, AP, India.

Variety	Parentage	Yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Test weight (g)	Seed dormancy (wk)	Grain type ^b	Reaction to BPH in field ^c	Year of release
MTU5249 (Vajram)	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	150	100	343	21.0	4	MS	3.0	1986
MTU5293 (Prathiba)	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	165	115	364	21.1	2	MS	2.0	1986
MTU2067 (Chaitanya)	Sowbhagya/ARC5984	6.5	155	110	390	21.5	4	MS	2.0	1988
MTU2077 (Krishnaveni)	Sowbhagya/ARC5984	6.5	155	110	405	19.7	4	MS	3.0	1989
MTU5182 (Nandi)	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	150	110	350	20.7	3	MS	2.0	1991
MTU4870	Sowbhagya/ARC6650	6.0	150	110	384	22.2	5	MS	2.0	-
Swarna (susceptible check)		-	150	105	360	20.0	3	MS	8.0	-

^aAll varieties have white kernels. ^bMS = medium slender. ^cScored using Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9.

Pest resistance—other pests

Susceptibility of wild rice species to nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

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We tested 15 accessions of 10 wild rice species to locate sources of resistance to the rice root knot nematode, *M. graminicola*. Eight-day-old seedlings of *Oryza australiensis* from Australia; *O. barthii* and *O. brachyantha* from Africa; *O. latifolia* from South and Central America; and *O. minuta*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinalis*, *O. rhizomatis*, *O. ridleyi*, and *O. rufipogon* from Asia were infested with 1,000 2d-stage juveniles of *M. graminicola* from a culture maintained on cultivar IR72 in a greenhouse.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, with six replications, in a greenhouse using 60-cm long, 10-cm diameter PVC tubes filled with 6 kg of sterilized soil. Six plants of each accession were grown under upland conditions and watered daily. Roots were collected 48 d after infestation. Second-stage juveniles were extracted by placing the roots in a misting chamber for 7 d. Results were analyzed

using ANOVA and DMRT.

M. graminicola reproduced on all of the wild rice species tested, indicating that none were resistant to the parasite (see table). Different degrees of susceptibility, however, were observed.

Average number of *M. graminicola* 2d-stage juveniles recovered from 1 g of root.

Wild rice species tested (accession no.)	<i>M. graminicola</i> juveniles recovered from 1 g of root ^a (av no.)
<i>O. australiensis</i> (100882)	10236 c
<i>O. barthii</i> (101827)	1672 a
<i>O. brachyantha</i> (101232)	5855 b
<i>O. latifolia</i> (100914)	761 a
<i>O. latifolia</i> (105141)	505 a
<i>O. latifolia</i> (105142)	469 a
<i>O. minuta</i> (101141)	1362 a
<i>O. nivara</i> (103422)	1024 a
<i>O. nivara</i> (103839)	3209 ab
<i>O. officinalis</i> (100896)	238 a
<i>O. rhizomatis</i> (105432)	650 a
<i>O. ridleyi</i> (100821)	452 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (100692)	872 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (103817)	965 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (104453)	396 a

^aAv of six replications. Averages followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

O. australiensis and *O. brachyantha* allowed greater reproduction of the parasite than did the other accessions. We will need to test other wild rice species and accessions of species previously tested to determine whether absolute resistance to rice root knot nematode exists in the genus *Oryza*. ■

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